

Deliverable D6.5 SUSTAINair Contributions to Standardization

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
AA	Aluminium Association
AMC	Acceptable Means of Compliance
AMS	Aerospace Materials Specification
ANS	Air Navigation Service
ATM	Air Traffic Management
BE	Beneficiary
CEN	Comité Européen de Normalisation
CM	Certification Memorandum
CS	Certification Specification
DO	Design Organisation
DOA	Design Organisation Approval
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EC	European Commission
EoL	End-of-Life
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
JAA	Joint Aviation Authority
MMPDS	Metallic Materials Properties Development and Standardization
N/A	Not applicable
PO	Production Organisation
POA	Production Organisation Approval
STC	Supplementary Type Certificate
TC	Type Certificate
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This public deliverable D6.5 is related to possible pathways for certification of innovations from SUSTAINair research outcomes to actual usage in series production of the aviation industry. Goal of this document is to provide an introduction to relevant aspects of certification and identify possible certification routes for SUSTAINair innovations, especially related to new or modified materials. As public deliverable it is meant to contribute to future investigations in that field by other RIA projects, aviation industry or other stakeholders in circular aviation.

To tackle this important topic, the SUSTAINair consortium cooperated with the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA). This report provides a summary of the results obtained in the course of this cooperation and especially the SUSTAINair Workshop on Contribution to Standardisation held on March 17th 2024 at EASA Headquarters in Cologne, Germany.

The report provides an outline and overview of the certification process for aviation industry in the European Union and an evaluation of selected SUSTAINair results compared to the identified certification routes. It investigates how SUSTAINair findings could be possibly implemented by the industry in near future and is the starting point of a roadmap to certification of SUSTAINair results.

The SUSTAINair consortium thanks the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) and especially Structures and Cabin Safety Expert Aiko Dühne for granting insights to standardization processes and contributions to this document.

1 INTRODUCTION

The research performed in SUSTAINair project involves several aircraft manufacturing topics such as new joining technologies, as well as novel aerospace grade materials, with the aim of achieving a sustainability increase of lightweight, multifunctional and intelligent airframe and engine parts. SUSTAINair investigates metal-composite joining by a novel pin-pattern created by additive manufacturing as well as thermoplastic composites welding. Furthermore, the application of production waste (from carbon fiber reinforced polymers as well as titanium and aluminium alloys, respectively) as well as end-of-life aircraft materials for recycling and remanufacturing is addressed, altogether aiming at a maturity level of TRL4. Being aware of the many steps needed to bring an innovation into operation, considerations are made related to the legal framework covering the airworthiness approvals for parts of aircraft or engines, respectively.

It is widely agreed that recycling and reuse offer significant improvement in energy consumption along the process chain. At the same time, the usage of waste streams (either from production or EoL) for generation of material used for the manufacturing of aviation products has to achieve the same level of safety as achieved by the primary material sources.

The European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) is not interfering into the manufacturing of substitute aerospace grade materials as long as the specifications of the materials are met, which were used for the design of the parts. It is the responsibility of the Production Organisation (PO) to use material grades of properties specified by the Design Organisation (DO) for every single part. In principle, there is no difference between new and recycled material, but it is widely known that both reuse and recycling of materials bury a plenitude of challenges in order to meet the specification of conventional types.

The main aim of this public deliverable titled “SUSTAINair Contributions to Standardization” is to spread knowledge about the (mandatory or recommended) procedures to bring new material compositions as well as standard materials with enhanced recycling content or even parts created by reusing material feedstock into aircraft operation, involving legally binding aspects of certification specifications for several kinds of aeroplanes and helicopters.

2 INTRODUCTION TO CERTIFICATION

The regulations for aviation safety, as we know them today, started to be developed in the US in the 1920s. With flying becoming more common, the need for rules and regulation became evident. With simple airworthiness standards in the early days, the rules were adapted after deficiencies were detected after accidents.

An example is the fatigue and damage tolerance regulation, which started off as a safe-life concept. With deadly accidents of the first commercial jetliner with a pressurized cabin, it showed that this approach is not enough to ensure the safety for this kind of aircraft. The fail-safe concept was introduced in 1958, assuming that an adequate safety level can be assured with a second load path.

However, 12 years later another deadly accident showed that this assumption was not correct. The horizontal tailplane of a Boeing 707 failed with 2 out of 3 attachments failed in fatigue

unnoticed. The consequence of this accident was, that the approach only works, if a maintenance program is ensuring that cracks can be detected before they become critical. And even this approach has been shown not to be adequate for all failure modes, which became evident with the Boeing 737 Aloha accident, where multiple fatigue cracks, below the inspectable crack length, linked all up resulting in the loss of a portion of the upper half of the fuselage. This led to the latest fatigue and damage tolerance requirements including the need to take widespread fatigue damage into account.

In addition, also in the 1920, the need for a regulatory oversight was seen to be necessary to develop new requirements and ensure their proper application. Over the years, a system in the US, overseen by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), was established to guarantee that aeronautical products are in compliance with the regulations. In Europe, all countries had their own aviation safety authority, often referring to the Certification Specification and associated regulations to the FAA system.

In the 1970s, during the times when also Airbus was founded, it became more important to have a common aviation regulation within Europe. The JAA (Joint Aviation Authority) was founded to ensure this by having multi-national teams investigating the certification of aeronautical products. Starting from the goal to have a common certification specification for large aircraft and engines, it widened its scope to all classes of aircraft and areas such as operations or maintenance. The JAA however only gave recommendations for e.g. the approval of an aircraft after the certification process, which then was used by national aviation authority to approve it.

In 2002 the EASA was founded, taking over the responsibility for the civil aviation in Europe from the national aviation authorities and concentrating all regulatory oversight in Europe in one place. Starting with the focus on certification of aeronautical products (including design organizations and production organizations), it expanded over time by taking over responsibility for air operations, crew licensing, drones, Urban Air Mobility, and other areas.

With more than 800 experts, the Agency covers all aviation domains, has agreements with 161 countries and international organisations, and oversees thousands of approved organisations and flight simulator training devices.

Regulatory Framework

The EASA regulatory framework is divided between a binding part, which is enforced by the European Parliament, European Council or European Commission, and a non-binding part which is established within EASA. Figure 1 provides a schematic overview of the regulatory framework.

Basic Regulation (Regulation EU 2018/1139)

The legal basis for the creation of the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) is the so called “Basic Regulation”, initially established with the Regulation (EC) 1592/2002. The current Basic Regulation is in force with the Regulation (EU) 2018/1139. This regulation is binding and is established by the European Parliament and the European Council.

This regulation defines EASA's competencies and was established to ensure a high and uniform level of protection of the European citizens in civil aviation. For that purpose, the Basic Regulation confers on the European Commission the power to adopt implementing and delegated acts which detail how to comply with the essential requirements of the Basic Regulation and regulate the subject matters included in its scope, in particular airworthiness, aircrew licensing, environmental compatibility related to products, aircraft operations including third-country operators, Air traffic management / air navigation services (ATM/ANS) including air traffic controllers licensing, aerodromes and ground handling, and unmanned aircraft.

Initial Airworthiness (Regulation (EU) 748/2012)

The rules for Airworthiness and Environmental Protection lays down in their Annex I, also known as "Part 21", implementing rules for the airworthiness and environmental certification of aircraft and related products, parts and appliances, as well as for the certification of design and production organisations.

The regulation itself is also binding and is established by the European Commission. However, the Acceptable Means of Compliance (AMC) for the Part 21 are non-binding established by EASA.

Certification Specification

The Certification Specifications (CS) with their AMC are established by EASA, laying down the technical requirements for the certification of a specific product. Some examples are CS 23 for small aircraft, CS 25 for large aircraft, CS 27 for small rotorcraft, CS 29 for large rotorcraft.

General AMC-20

General AMC-20 are written to give further guidance on the certification of products, parts or appliances which cover several different certification specifications. One example, which is related to materials, is the AMC 20-29 laying down further guidance to certify composite materials.

Certification Memorandum

A Certification Memorandum (CM) gives further guidance for showing compliance to certain subjects, such as for example large antennas or external loads. These CM can be transferred to an AMC at a later stage if deemed necessary.

Regulatory Framework

Figure 1: Overview of the EASA regulatory framework.

The Certification Process

In order to build a new aircraft type (new type certificate) or to change a part on a certified type, a certification process with the competent authority has to be undergone, ending in an approval of the changed design. The competent authority in Europe is EASA. Within a certification process there are different types of processes, described further in Part 21. For example, a Type Certificate (TC) holder can apply for a change or repair to the type design for which he is the TC holder, any other design organization can apply for a Supplemental Type Certificate (STC). Other forms are minor changes or minor repairs, for which no design organization is necessary. Once the certification process is finalized, the certified parts can be manufactured and installed in accordance with the data provided by the TC/STC holder. Within these processes, the actors have different responsibilities.

Design Organisation

A Design Organization (DO) has certain responsibilities and privileges. In order to apply for a major change or a major repair, a design organization approval is necessary. This is granted when certain procedures are in place to ensure that all data produced by this organization are at the needed quality to ensure the safety of the product. Some examples are an independent quality system, a minimum qualification of the personnel and independent checking functions of all compliance data produced. An important privilege a DO can obtain is the approval of minor changes and minor repairs without the application to EASA.

Production organization

A Production Organization (PO) is needed to build aeronautical products. As for the DO, the PO needs to fulfil certain quality standards ensuring that the products manufactured are in line with the design data provided by the DO. A PO can release a part with an EASA Form 1, or an aircraft with a Form 52, which is an authorized release certificate stating that the product was manufactured in accordance with approved design data. Only parts with a Form 1 are eligible to be installed on an aircraft.

Certification of Materials

Within the certification process, products are certified to be installed on an aircraft. However, EASA is only certifying this product and not explicitly the materials it is made of.

A certified product consists of drawings specifying the dimensions, tolerances, fasteners and material to be used. During the certification process, it is substantiated that the referenced material is suitable for the use and able to sustain the static and fatigue loading. If aviation grade material is referenced, it does not mean that this material is certified, approved or by any other means accepted by EASA.

The requirements regarding material certification are embedded in the different layers of regulations and requirements listed in the chapter “regulatory framework”.

Basic Regulation

In Annex II of the basic regulation the essential requirements for airworthiness are established. These requirements are binding, meaning that no derogation (as possible for non-binding rules) is possible.

In chapter 1 of Annex II of the basic regulation the product integrity is addressed. For materials it is stated: “The production processes and materials used in the construction of the aircraft must result in known and reproducible structural properties. Any changes in material performance related to the operational environment must be accounted for.”

This means it must be ensured that the materials used in production comply with the materials specified in the design organization's drawings.

Part 21

The requirements laid down in Part 21 are also binding and therefore no derogation is possible. Amongst others, the requirements for Design Organizations and Productions Organizations are specified.

In Part 21 Subpart J “Design Organization Approval” is requiring that the product under certification complies to the applicable specification and requirements. Therefore, the DOA is responsible for ensuring that the referenced material has design properties which are in

compliance with the Certification specification for the relevant product (e.g. CS 23, CS 25, CS 27...).

In Part 21 Subpart G “Production Organization Approval” (POA), the rights and obligations of the POA are specified. The POA is obligated to establish a quality system to ensure that the material purchased conforms with the material specification the DOA has established. This must include auditing vendors and sub-contractors to ensure that the process and quality control is in line with expectations, verification of the incoming materials, and correct identification and traceability. If the POA has performed the needed steps to ensure that the part manufactured is in line with the DOA drawing, a Form 1 is issued, allowing installation of the part on an aeronautical product.

Certification Specification (CS) and Acceptable Means of Compliance (AMC)

Since the CS and its AMC are so called “soft law”, the requirements are not binding. However, if not used, the applicant has to either ensure an equivalent level of safety or, as a minimum, show compliance to the essential requirement of the Basic Regulation.

The CS and AMC are establishing the requirements the DOA must take into account when design a part. For Materials, the paragraphs CS 2X.603 (Materials), CS 2X.605 (Fabrication Methods) and 2X.613 (Material strength properties and Material Design Values) and their associated AMC material are the key requirement. It is stated that the suitability and durability of the material is established based on experience or test, it must conform to an approved specification and the environment has to be considered. Especially the approved specifications are a core requirement, which the material's manufacturer must consider. However, the responsibility to confirm that the material is made in accordance with the specifications is with the POA.

Summary

The responsibility that the correct materials are used in aeronautical products is with the POA. The (raw) material manufacturer has no direct obligation towards EASA and has no specific approval. Within the oversight of the POA, the material manufacturer provides proof to the POA that the material conforms to the specification given to him. There is no difference between new and recycled material. Also the material specified by the DOA need not necessarily be a material specified within the standard material handbooks like MMPDS. However, if any other materials are used, the DOA must ensure that the specified material has the design properties assumed in the design. The POA then needs to ensure that the material manufacturer meets these specifications.

3 ROUTES TO CERTIFICATION OF RECYCLED MATERIALS

In the previous section it was pointed out that materials are not certified by themselves. Instead, a DO will specify the use of certain materials in a design, and then show that the design incorporating those materials meets all the CS requirements. Subsequently the PO has to show that all products actually produced are made with the materials specified in the design.

For recycled materials, the objective should therefore not be to certify the material, but rather to ensure the material is ready to be incorporated into the certification process described above, by providing necessary material properties and demonstrating the maturity and stability of the manufacturing process. In this process material specifications play a big role. Therefore, developers of recycled materials, aiming to supply to the aviation industry, need to ensure that their materials are 'specifiable', for which two possible routes can be identified:

- (1) produce recycled material to existing standards, or
- (2) produce recycled material to new standards.

Produce to Existing Standard

In their design, a DO will specify the material to be used, according to certain specifications. These specifications can be proprietary to a materials supplier, or they can be defined by a third party. The latter is common for metal alloys.

For example, the North American Aluminium Association (AA) developed a designation system for wrought alloys, which has also been adopted by the International Organisation for Standardization (ISO) and the Comité Européen de Normalisation (CEN)¹. Similarly, SAE International (formally the Society of Automotive Engineers) has developed the Aerospace Material Specifications (AMS) system. In the AA system, a four-digit number is used to designate a specific alloy and a letter followed by another number is used to designate the temper. So, for example, the code AA 2024-T3 refers to a specific alloy composition (90.7-94.7% Al, 3.8-4.9% Cu, 1.2-1.8% Mg, 0.3-0.9% Mn) and temper (Solution heat treated, cold worked, and naturally aged to a substantially stable condition). When new alloys are developed, they can be registered in this system, and then unambiguously referred to via the assigned code.

By having a strict definition on the chemical content and heat treatment, if such a registered designation is specified, the material properties will reliably fall into a relatively narrow range. For many materials commonly used in aerospace, these values can be found in the 'Metallic Materials Properties Development and Standardization (MMPDS)' handbook², which is currently maintained by the Battelle Memorial institute.

The advantage of this designation system is that it is supplier agnostic. The DO simply specifies the use of a specific alloy and temper, and the PO is then free to source the material from any supplier, as long as the right quality controls are in place to ensure the supplied material meets

¹ European Aluminium Association (2022), *The Aluminium Automotive Manual*

² <https://www.mmpds.org/>

all the specified characteristics. So, for example, the DO may call out in a drawing that a specific component should be made from AA 2024-T3, and then the PO can purchase a batch of AA 2024-T3 from any supplier, as long as they can guarantee that the delivered material indeed complies with the specifications for AA2024-T3.

The existing metal material specifications define the alloy's chemical make-up, i.e. which atoms it should contain, but not the source of those atoms. In other words, the material specifications do not make a distinction between alloys made directly from mined materials, or alloys made (partially or fully) from recycled materials. This creates a rather straightforward path for 'certification' of recycled metals, at least conceptually. As long as it can be shown that the output of a recycling process reliably produces an alloy meeting a specific material specification, no further action is needed. The material can be inserted into the normal production route and treated no differently to the same alloy made from virgin material. The challenge here will be setting up the production process and quality controls to ensure that the alloy composition and temper can be guaranteed to match the specification.

For composite materials, typically material specifications are developed by the material suppliers directly. So, for example, IM7/8552 is an older generation carbon fibre / epoxy composite used in aerospace, and also very popular in academic research. Here, IM7 refers to a specific grade of carbon fibre, and 8552 to a particular epoxy resin system. Both codes are proprietary to Hexcel, the material manufacturer. This means that if the design calls for the use of IM7/8552, the PO cannot get the material from a different supplier, unless they are able to establish via an extensive test programme that the new material is identical to the IM7/8552 specification in all relevant ways.

Of course, when developing a recycled material, it would be rather difficult to show compliance to a proprietary material specification, without having the cooperation of the owner of that material specification. Furthermore, with the current state of the art, recycling of composite materials typically results in some degrading of properties, indicating that the recycled material will not meet the original material specification. Therefore a different approach is needed for recycling composite materials.

Produce to New Standard

If it is not possible to produce a recycled material to match an existing specification, instead a new specification could be developed. The key here is consistency and reliability. The DO will specify the material to be used during the design stage. They therefore need to be confident that a material having the required properties will remain available throughout the expected production run of the new aircraft. This implies that the recycling process must be stable and the output well defined, so that the material supplier can guarantee that any material batch, now and in the future, will match the specification. It also implies that the recycling process needs to be capable of dealing with variability in the input, to nevertheless produce a consistent output product.

In order for the 'new specification' route to be viable, a DO needs to be able to rely on the idea that if they specify a certain material, then that material will always meet or exceed the required material properties, regardless of the batch or manufacturer. Thus, to enable this material certification route, the material supplier needs to demonstrate that the material consistently and

reliably meets the required properties, and that the variability in material properties is under control, as described in more detail in the next section.

Dealing with Variability

Especially for recycled materials, material property variability is a concern. Of course, a proper material specification should seek to limit and control the variability of the material properties, because a DO needs to be able to rely on the fact that specifying a certain material will result in certain material properties. Nevertheless, some variability of material properties is inevitable (also for virgin materials) and therefore needs to be allowed and accounted for by proper design practices. This involves the selection of suitable design allowables, which take into account the statistical variation in material properties, measured during material qualification. An example of this can for example be found in CS25.613, which specifies so-called 'A' and 'B' basis material design values. In case of an A basis value (to be used for single load path structures), the design allowable must be chosen such that the material strength is assured with a probability of 99% with a confidence of 95%. The B basis value on the other hand requires that the material property is assured with a probability of 90% with a confidence of 95%.

Fully describing the statistics underlying the development of A and B basis values goes beyond the scope of this report, but an abbreviated discussion will be provided to give some feeling for the process to those unfamiliar with it. For more details, the reader may consult for example the Composite Materials Handbook 17 (CMH-17)³. A detailed worked example can be found in the NIAR statistical analysis report on a TenCate glass fibre reinforce epoxy composite (Clarkson, 2017)⁴.

At a conceptual level, A and B bases can be calculated via the following equation:

$$basis = \bar{X} - kS$$

where \bar{X} is the mean value of the property of interest (e.g. strength), S is the standard deviation and k is a factor that depends on the number of specimens tested and the statistical distribution of the test data. As an example, Figure 2 shows the k -factor, assuming a normal distribution applies to the test data. It can be seen that if only 10 specimens are tested, obtaining the A-basis requires subtracting 4 times the standard deviation from the mean test value, whereas the B-basis still requires subtracting 2.3 times the standard deviation. A nice illustration of the effect of the number of specimens tested in case of a Weibull distribution can be found in a conference paper presented by Nettles at the 2004 International Conference on Composites Engineering (available from the NASA Technical Reports Server)⁵.

³ <https://www.cmh17.org/>

⁴ Clarkson (2017) *TenCate Advance Composites S2 Unitape with BT250E-6 Resin Material Allowables Statistical Analysis Report*, NIAR Report Number: NCP-RP-2015-021 N/C, https://www.wichita.edu/industry_and_defense/NIAR/Research/tencate-bt250e-6/TenCate-Advance-Composite-S2-Unitape-with-BT250E-6-Resin-Material-Allowables-Statistical-Analysis-Report.pdf

⁵ Alan T. Nettles (2004), *Allowables for Structural Composites*, International Conference on Composites Engineering, <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20040111395>

Figure 2: *k*-factors as a function of number of specimens tested for a normal distribution, based on the estimation equations given in Clarkson (2017)

To give a numerical example, imagine we test a material and find a mean tensile strength of 560 MPa, with a standard deviation of 10%. Assuming the material obeys a normal distribution, and we tested 10 samples, then the B-basis allowable would be $560 - 2.3 * 56 = 428$ MPa, and the A-basis allowable would be only $560 - 3.98 * 56 = 337$ MPa. If instead we would test 100 samples (assuming the standard deviation remains at 10%), the B-basis allowable would increase to 474 MPa, while the A-basis allowable would now be 409 MPa.

This example shows that there is a trade-off between the cost of testing more specimens (to reduce the *k*-factor) and accepting a lower design allowable. In any case, a significant testing effort will be required to generate acceptable values. Nettles (2004) points out that a minimum of 10 specimens is required to be tested to even attempt a Weibull analysis. The Clarkson (2017) report was based on 18-22 specimens per test condition, per property. As 5 properties were measured for 3 environmental conditions and an additional property was measured at 4 environmental conditions, this represents about 400 specimens tested, giving some feeling for the effort required to qualify a new material, especially if one considers that such a characterisation may need to be repeated for different lay-ups.

It is important to note that while material property variability can be allowed, the value of the A and B basis property will directly depend on the standard deviation of the material property, and thus reducing the standard deviation as much as is feasible is of paramount importance. Furthermore, it is necessary to ensure that there is a long term consistency of the standard deviation. Because if there is a large batch-to-batch variability for example, that would imply that the A and B bases need to be developed by combining results from many different samples, which may need to be collected over a long term from different production runs. Another alternative could be that A and B basis generation testing would have to be repeated for each new batch of material, which would likely be prohibitively expensive. Therefore, for a recycling process, there likely needs to be some level of quality control on the input pre-recycling material, or some mechanism in the manufacturing process that can ensure consistency of the output material, even when faced with variability of the inputs.

Introducing a New Material

Once a material qualification strategy has been chosen (i.e. produce to an existing specification, or create a new specification), and the necessary manufacturing and quality control process are in place (and validated), the recycled material can be introduced into the market.

If the recycled material is produced to an existing standard, this is straightforward. A PO can simply purchase the material and include it in a product without further action, as the material complies with the specified design.

On the other hand, if a recycled material is produced to a new specification, then including this material in a design implies a change of material, i.e. a design change. This requires the DO to conduct an evaluation and show that the design is still compliant with all requirements when the new material is used. In part, this will require showing that the new material meets the required A or B basis design allowables. As illustrated in the previous subsection, such an analysis will require a lot of work, as it will necessitate both qualifying the new material, and potentially require redoing previous structural analyses (for example, if the previous design allowables cannot be exactly matched or exceeded). Therefore, DOs will likely want to avoid such a material replacement unless there is a very compelling business case.

For large aircraft, introduction of a recycled material therefore should likely wait for the development of a new design, where structural analyses and tests are required anyway, and thus the marginal cost of introducing a new material rather than a more familiar one would be limited. Given the long design cycles and a time between new aircraft designs on the order of decades, this creates a tricky situation for suppliers of recycled materials.

Instead, it could be better to target smaller, general aviation (GA) aircraft, such as certified under CS23. These manufacturers are more used to having to replace materials, as, due to their limited order volume, they typically have more challenges maintaining stable material supplies and thus are more used to replacing materials on existing products. Therefore, they might be more able and willing to introduce a recycled material as replacement for a currently used material, either due to a compelling financial business case, or to enhance the sustainability of their design.

4 CERTIFIABILITY ANALYSIS OF SUSTAINAIR RESULTS

In this chapter, the main results of SUSTAINair are listed and analyzed with respect to needs of certification efforts, following the certification strategies identified in the previous chapter.

#	Result	BE(s)	KET(s)	CERTIFIABILITY ANALYSIS
1	Adapted plasma-torch design for improved gas flow. New/adapted design: Adaption of the patented plasma torch by implementation of additional flow channels (shielding gas for Cu-tracks or O ₂ for ZnO-Synthesis)	INO; JR	KET 6	N/A ¹
2	Induction welding of 1st life PPS and LM-PAEK samples : New dataset: Lap shear strength data of SLS specimens welded at four different temperatures	NLR	KET 2 KET 3	PO must produce according to new specification, need more data on variability and to develop a stable process
3	Induction welding of 2nd life PPS samples : New dataset: Induction welding process data and lap shear strength data of SLS specimens on recycled material	NLR	KET 2 KET 3	PO must produce according to new specification, need more data on variability and to develop a stable process
4	Online monitoring of temperatures during induction welding using an optical sensor: New measurement methods: Using an optical sensor (FBG) to measure temperatures during induction welding	NLR	KET 2 KET 3	N/A ²
5	Experimental Demonstration of Electrical Resistance Measurements (ERM) as potential SHM method for hybrid SLS specimen : new application of method	JKU	KET 6	N/A ²
6	Novel multi-method SHM concept for hybrid SLS specimen with reduced cabling effort : new application of methods	JKU	KET 6	N/A ²

7	Zinc oxide nanomaterial syntheses by atmospheric pressure plasma deposition : New material syntheses process	JR; INO	KET 6	N/A ²
8	Sensor with sandwich structure manufactured : New sensor design	JR	KET 6	N/A ²
9	Oriented electro-spun fabrics including nanowires : New sensor design	JR	KET 6	N/A ²
10	Laser welding of Ti64 and cast-cast (AlMgSi-X, w/o filler wire) and wrought-wrought (6xxx+, standard 6063 filler wire) coupon combination , manufactured by laser-based powder bed fusion : New application of method	JR	n/a	PO must achieve weldment properties according to design requirements.
11	Coupons/specimens manufactured with reused Ti64 powder in a modified LPBF machine : Modified process: integration of gas purification system in LPBF machine	DLR	KET 4	PO has to prove that that applying reused Ti64 powder meets the design requirements.
12	Hybrid joints with pins (preliminary tests) : Ti64-CFRP joints with additively manufactured interface features for improved joint performance	DLR; INVENT ; TUD; JKU	KET 7	N/A ³
13	AlMgSi HPDC alloy with high iron tolerance : Adapted composition for commercial higher performance AlMgSi alloys with an increased Fe/Zn/Cu tolerance by factor 3-4 via nanoeutectic composition adaption.	AIT-LKR	KET 5	PO has to prove that that the alloy modification is meeting the design requirements. Developing a new alloy specification may be required.
14	High temperature tooling for direct short duration solid solution heat treatment of high performance alloys in HPDC : HPDC tool design (dry tests already executed) that allows direct solution heat treatment of alloys in HPDC tool, hence allowing direct production of delicate high performance alloy parts with complex structures	AIT-LKR	KET 5	N/A ¹

15	Laminate made with 2nd life material : New composition: combination of 1st life surface layers and 2nd life core material. Two grades of 2nd life material were used to create two varieties of laminate.	DTC	KET 3	A new specification has to be developed covering this material concept.
17	Conduction welding of 2nd life PPS samples : New dataset: Conduction welding process data and lap shear strength data of SLS specimens on recycled material	DTC	KET 2 & 7	PO has to prove that that joints are meeting the design requirements
18	Development of tooling for continuous forming of 1st and 2nd life laminates on CCM equipment : New process: using multi-action tooling to create 2,5D-profiles on 2D CCM equipment.	DTC	KET 3	N/A ¹
19	Press tool for 2nd life Material and process parameters for upcycling of aviation certified prepreg waste : New process: reuse of prepreg scraps from series production	INVENT	n/a	N/A ¹
20	Integration of Piezo patch sensors in 2nd life CFRP coupon specimens : New process: Adaptation of prepreg scrap upcycling process for sensor integration	INVENT ; JKU	n/a	N/A ²
21	Additive manufacturing and/or repair of Al-alloys by L-DED : New application of method	JR; AIT-LKR	KET 5	PO must prove that AM structures (and joints to previous parts in case of repair) are meeting the design requirements. DO must show that the design requirements are suitable.
22	Titanium micro-pins using CMT	AIT-LKR	KET 7	N/A ³
23	Detachable joint between flexible (FKM) and rigid (CFRP) joining partners utilizing functional interlayers	INVENT	KET1	PO must prove that joints are meeting the design requirements. DO must show that design requirements are suitable.

24	Detachable joint utilizing Thermal Expanding Particles (TEPs)	INVENT	KET1	PO must prove that joints are meeting the design requirements. DO must show that design requirements are suitable.
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N/A¹: not applicable with respect to material certification because it is part of a manufacturing equipment; a PO is responsible for the application of a new equipment and the achievement of the required properties created by applying a adapted equipment)

N/A²: not applicable as long as a remaining sensor (e.g. optical fibre) is not influencing material / part properties

N/A³: not applicable given that approved materials are involved; then rules for structural concepts apply.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The Deliverable “SUSTAINair Contributions to Standardization” has highlighted that it is somewhat of a misconception to talk about ‘certification of recycled materials’ in an airworthiness concept, as EASA only certifies products, which may or may not contain recycled materials. The materials themselves are not certified.

Instead, a design organisation will show that if a material conforming to a certain specification is used in the design, then the design fulfils all the relevant requirements. Then the production organisation has to prove that they indeed manufacture all their products in accordance with the design, which includes the material specification.

Thus ‘certification of recycled materials’ should be understood as developing the recycling process to a level where the material can be included in this existing certification process. This means either manufacturing recycled material that conforms to an already existing material specification, or to develop a new material specification for the recycled material, which could then be included in a design. In both cases, it is important to control the quality and variability of the recycling process, in order to ensure that the produced material consistently and reliably conforms to the specification.

The technologies developed in SUSTAINair were analyzed according to these possible certification routes. For cases where a new material concept (rather than structural design concept or manufacturing process) was developed, the route of developing a new material specification will be necessary. For the AlMgSi HPDC alloy with high iron tolerance, it may be possible to manufacture this to an existing standard, but if its composition is too far from the existing standard, a new standard will have to be developed as well.

As a final conclusion, and a recommendation to the R&D community working on recycled materials, the key is to have sufficient control of the recycling process so that it can be ensured that the output will always confirm to a fixed specification.

6 REFERENCES

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